

DETERMINATION OF THE INTERFACIAL SHEAR STRENGTH
BY FIBRE FRAGMENTATION IN RESIN SYSTEMS WITH A SMALL RUPTURE STRAIN

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ABSTRACT

The Fraser-DiBenedetto monofilament test has been extensively used for matrix systems of sufficient elongation and toughness, but a limitation is met when applied to the brittle resins currently used in CFRP due to the breakage of the test sample at the first fibre rupture. Attention is put in the paper on the possibility of performing the test by taking a redesigned sample : the fibre is first embedded in the resin system to be evaluated and the whole sample then encapsulated in a compliant and crack-resisting resin. Preliminary results with a set of carbon fibres and Narmco 5208 as the resin system are given and discussed along with data from the standard pull-out tests.

INTRODUCTION

The conditions of stress-transfer at the fibre/matrix interface are of the utmost importance for optimizing the properties of composite materials and do not confine themselves to the limited "adhesion" point of view : essential features such as fibre efficiency, toughness, stress-redistribution etc... are tightly related to the actual conditions of stress-transfer.

At the fibre production level, it is quite desirable to dispose of a screening test to improve or reject a line of surface treatments or coatings without having recourse to the tedious and matter-consuming manufacturing a composite control-part. As far as the fibre/matrix stress-transfer characteristics are concerned, such a test was first proposed by Fraser and DiBenedetto [1] : a resin specimen containing one single filament (with $\epsilon_{mR} > \epsilon_{fR}$ where ϵ_{mR} and ϵ_{fR} are the rupture strains of the matrix and the fibre, respectively) is loaded in tension. When the specimen strain reaches ϵ_{fR} , the fibre breaks ; the fibre fracturing process then continues as ϵ keeps increasing, until a limit when fragments are too short to be stressed to rupture.

Measuring the average fragment length gives the critical length l_c and the interfacial shear strength τ which is simply given by Eq. 1 :

$$\frac{\tau}{\sigma_{fR}(l_c)} = \frac{d_f}{2l_c} \quad (1)$$

In Eq. 1, $\sigma_{fR}(l_c)$ stands for the tensile strength of the fibre of length l_c as the gage length effect on the fibre strength has to be taken into account ; d_f is the fibre diameter.

The recent literature gives several examples of the application of the technique to glass [1-3], carbon [4-6] and even Kevlar [7] fibres. Notice has to be taken however that the tests are always performed with a resin such that $\epsilon_{MR}/\epsilon_{FR}$ is at least 3 : the latter condition is experimentally imposed by the requirement for the fragments to reach the minimal length before total breakage of the resin sample : Eq. 1 is valid only when the fragmentation has been completed.

When the fragmentation technique offers an interesting way to assess the quality of the interface, it has been restricted up to now to resins with a high strain capability. Three limitations have been currently recognized when one considers the most recent systems of fibres and thermosetting resins for aeronautical structures :

- (i) low strain to failure and high crack-sensitivity of the matrix
- (ii) relatively higher strain to failure of the fibre (up to 1.8% for T800 type fibres)
- (iii) strong adhesion which implies a short critical length and, therefore, through the gage length effect, a possibly still higher rupture strain of the shorter fibre fragments.

The communication first gives the results for systems with a DGEBA resin which has enough elongation to allow the technique to be applied directly. Then follows a description of the modifications brought to the method to make it applicable to "brittle" resins of the TGDDM type. Afferent data are also given. In both cases, values are compared with the results of the standard pull-out testing according to [8].

FRAGMENTATION WITH A TOUGH AND COMPLIANT RESIN

The resin we used (Araldite LY556 + HT972) has a strain to failure of about 6% (Table 1) which makes it suitable for fibre fragmentation experiments. Dog-bone specimens containing a 30 mm length axially oriented single fibre were loaded in tension until full fragmentation has been achieved. The progressive fracture was monitored by acoustic emission : figure 1 displays a load-displacement curve with most of the events recorded in the central portion when the stress is monotonically increasing. The situation is propitious indeed as the material emits no noise during the last part of the test, allowing to conclude that "saturation", i.e. full fragmentation, really occurred and stop the test before final fracture. On account of the progressive work-hardening of the

material, any risk of a premature saturation due to a possible plastic flow of the matrix can be also eliminated.

TABLE 1
Material properties

Matrix

Type		E (GPa)	σ_R (MPa)	ϵ_R (%)	K_{IC} (MPa/m)
DGEBA	Araldite LY556 + HT972 (2H/140°C)	2.7	94.1	5.7	1.05
TGDDM	Narmco 5208 (2H/180°C)	4.0	79.1	2.4	0.47

30 mm length samples for tension - CTS specimens for K_{IC} .

Fibre

Type	\emptyset (μm)	σ_R (GPa)	Weibull parameters		
			m	σ_1	C.V. (%)
COURTAULDS Grafil HT	7.62	2.77	3.55	3.07	39
TORAYKA T300 50B	6.90	3.83	7.83	3.83	17

12 mm gage length.

The number and length of broken fibre pieces were determined either from AE signals or directly by microscopic examination of the (transparent) samples. As reported elsewhere [3, 5, 11], an adequate setting of the AE equipment results in a one to one correspondence between the number of acoustic pulses and the observations. The critical length was then derived using the approximation of OHSAWA [2] that $l_c = 4/3 l$ where l is the mean length of the fragments. A cumulative number of 100 to 150 fragments was considered to form a sufficient set of data for each fibre/matrix combination.

Fig. 1. Load and acoustic activity (in counts/second) versus displacement. System : HT/LY556.

The fibre strength at $l = l_c$ in Eq. 1 is determined from the 2-parameters Weibull distribution established by tensile testing a number of single fibres at fixed gage length and assuming an unique mode of rupture. Even though the reliability of the Weibull treatment for carbon fibres has been discussed several times in the recent literature [6, 9, 10], a good estimation of σ_R ($l = l_c$) is of critical importance to calculate absolute τ values and make valuable comparisons between fibres or surface treatments. The fibre diameter is the average of a number of determinations with SEM.

Table 2 gives typical results obtained with our reference system (HT fibre, untreated, unsized, cf. Table 1). It turns out that confidence can be put on the method in consideration of the good reproductibility. In the table, fibre # 2 may have been of smaller diameter than the four others which resulted in a comparatively larger τ (remember that the same diameter is taken for one batch of fibres).

TABLE 2
Interfacial shear strength τ
from fragmentation tests of 5 samples
(Fibre : HT ; Matrix : Araldite LY556)

#	N_{EA}	N_{OBS}	l_c (μm)	$\sigma_{fR}(l=l_c)$ (GPa)	τ (MPa)
1	24	25	1613	4.84	11.4
2	28	29	1340	5.10	14.5
3	25	25	1614	4.84	11.4
4	26	26	1532	4.92	12.2
5	26	26	1505	4.94	12.5

N_{EA} : number of AE events (= fragments - 1)

N_{OBS} : number of observed fragments, used here to calculate τ

In Table 3, values of τ for several fibres with the same DGEBA matrix have been listed. There is a strong evidence from both fragmentation and pull-out testing that the interfacial shear strength is higher with treated fibres. Data for the T300 fibre are of particular interest : untreated and treated fibres definitely give distinct fragment lengths (and τ) whereas there is almost no change in pull-out strengths, which confirms that different mechanisms are addressed in each mode of stressing the interface.

TABLE 3
Interfacial shear strength
for various fibre/matrix systems

Resin type (Table 1)	Basic fibre (Table 1)	TREATMENT	SIZING	τ (MPa)	τ PULL-OUT (MPa)
DGEBA	HT	NO	NO	12.2	28.0
		YES(*)	NO	44.0	65.5
		YES(**)	NO	37.3	-
	T 300	NO	NO	30.5	55
		YES	NO	46.3	58
		YES	YES	47.8	59
TGDDM	HT	NO	NO	NO SUCCESS	60
TGDDM/ DGEBA	HT	NO	NO	21.7	60(+)
		YES(**)	NO	58.3	-
	T 300	NO	NO	54.0	133(+)
		YES	NO	63.2	-
		YES	YES	-	150(+)

(*) treated fibres according to [8]

(**) commercial treatment (HTS fibres)

(+) fibres pulled-out from the TGDDM matrix alone

FRAGMENTATION WITH A BRITTLE RESIN

As reported in Table 3, the test is unsuccessful with the TGDDM resin system due to both the high crack-sensitivity of the organic material (cf. Table 1) and the strong adhesion : the specimens actually break into two pieces at the first fibre fracture as it has been observed for a long time by many authors [12, 13].

Under these new conditions, the technique ought to be modified when a matrix whose the rupture strain is reduced by a severe brittleness is used in a fragmentation test.

A modification has been evaluated, which consists in coating the fibre with a thin sheath of the selected resin (TGDDM type, Table 1), then embedding the coated fibre into a more ductile resin which acts as a support to maintain the specimen integrity. Coating is made by slight rubbing along a single fibre with a drop of resin ; experimental parameters have to be well adjusted to obtain a thin and regular sheath. After curing, the core/sheath fibres are moulded into the same dog-bone specimens as before with an excess of the ductile DGEBA resin (fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Idealized view of the tensile specimen. (The specimens actually are provided with holes and the fibre ends taken away by precision machining before getting ready for tests).

When such a "bimatrix" specimen is loaded in tension, each fibre rupture induces a fracture of the brittle sheath by crack propagation. However, this "penny shape crack" is now stopped by the tougher support at the second interface thus preventing the complete fracture of the specimen.

Whereas in the direct fragmentation the micromechanical aspects rather are well founded, the existence of two interfaces in the "bimatrix"

specimens involves a more complex situation (fig. 3) : the fibre ends, on each side of a fracture, are reloaded in the ordinary way through shear stresses by the TGDDM resin, but the latter itself is reloaded by the DGEBA support. The recorded values of l_c are expected to be a combination of the lengths of stress transfer at both interfaces.

Fig. 3. Stress distribution near a crack in the bimatrix sample.

As a result, the experimental values of τ given in Table 3 and calculated with Eq. 1, do not strictly represent the true values of the fibre/TGDDM interfacial shear strength, but underestimated values.

To assess the expected deviation, it must be pointed out that the sliding friction which appears after interface debonding primarily depends on the fibre surface state but also on the residual thermal stresses and the normal stresses caused by the tensile loading. The support resin does likely contribute to the last two stresses. On the other hand, the thermal

expansion and Poisson ratio both are considered to be quite similar for the matrix and support resins ; together with the assumption that the resin/resin interface remains elastically bonded throughout the test, it follows that the length of stress transfer at this interface will be small, compared to the fibre/resin interface (see fig. 3). Values of τ characteristic of the searched interface can thus be deduced.

As can be seen from the results listed in the last part of Table 3, the interfacial shear strength strongly increases when using a TGDDM matrix. The improvement is equivalent, though not in the absolute values, to what is observed with the pull-out test when surface-treated fibres are tested. As far as the absolute values are concerned, the above discussion emphasized some disadvantages of the technique and the lower τ could have been predicted. It is fair to admit that the pull-out testing itself may be sometimes confusing.

CONCLUSION

The Fraser-DiBenedetto method of evaluating the fibre/resin interface properties through fibre fragmentation offers some useful features as it gives indications on the basic mechanisms of the stress-transfer : debonding, friction, matrix yield... It is thus highly desirable to use the method when one has to deal with the surface treatments of carbon fibres, as it has been made for glass.

However, the fragmentation tests have been so far limited to systems with a compliant and relatively tough matrix and the resins associated to the carbon fibres, generally rigid, brittle and adhering strongly to the fibres do not meet the requirements of the test.

A modification has been proposed in the paper to go beyond this limit : the fibre to be evaluated is first coated with the resin ; the coated sample is then embedded into another, but tough, matrix.

As it has been discussed, the new technique does not claim to give a "true" value of the interfacial shear strength due to the existence of a dual interface. But it offers an interesting way to appreciate the effects of fibre surface treatments for the real systems of resins.

Some preliminary results have been presented : the ratios untreated/treated fibres of τ values are reasonably similar whatever the resin was used as the matrix ; so it is with the DGEBA/TGDDM ratios of τ when one type of fibres is considered. Agreement with the pull-out test

results is also nearly verified as far as ratios are concerned.

The conclusion could be that any compliant and crack-resisting resin is suitable to estimate the effects of the surface treatment of carbon fibres. Additional tests with other matrices and surface treatments are required to confirm the conclusion.

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